

ONLINE TEACHING “HANDS-ON” WHILE COVID: A DIGITAL SERVICE ENGINEERING TRAINING COURSE

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Abstract

Purpose – *The idea was to deliver an academic educational online course with very practical elements during the COVID pandemic for future service engineers. The practical course module during the COVID pandemic of this project is to produce a working paper on how an online training program for a future service engineer could look like.*

Methodology - *Survey of literature and industrialists to identify essential scientific methods with practical relevance for services development.*

Findings – *A course model has been developed with a lot of “hands-on exercises which helps students to develop services in small teams online.*

Practical implications – *The developed online course model is highly practical and delivers similar results as in classroom. But a special focus is on the lecturer to always keep track on the online communication of the participants.*

Originality/value – *The course concept -originally designed for the specific COVID limitations and requirements- can also be used for all kinds of trainings with dislocated participants such as industrialists from different branches or geographically distributed students.*

Key words: *Education, Service Engineering, Online Training Class*

Transition from Traditional to Modern Business Models

Digital transformation means a re-orientation of products, services, processes and business models towards the continuously digitalised world and results in faster transactions and more reliability through quality and security and therefore leads to higher customer satisfaction. [Kreutzer Ralf T., 2017]

This is only possible, if companies can digitalise information and data about products, customers, processes and services and thereby digitally transform their business model. With this new working method, a high amount of data is collected about business procedures and production processes, customer demands, as well as data about internal and external communication, requiring a high amount of management and data analysis.

Such a business approach leads to the engineering of all kinds of industrial services (XaaS- Everything as a service). The regular pathway of transformation follows typically in three generic phases as described in Fig. 1:

Figure 1 shows the pathways towards a digital business. By this it is essential to master internal and external challenges within an enterprise. A stringent fully digital business requires to digitize both side of the interaction.

Fig. 1. Digital transformation (modified and enhanced according to [2])

This begins through the digitalisation of the channels and processes used to create or provide value. Afterwards, the digitalisation of products, services and other objects are included in the value chain. Finally, a full digitalisation of all transactions and procedures with a high automation level leads to a fully digitalised business model [Dehmer; Kutzera, Niemann, 2017].

Fig.2. Process Model for Business Model Innovation (modified and enhanced according to [6])

New business models such as pay-per-use (usage-based payment e.g.: Car2go), peer-to-peer (trade between private individuals e.g.: Airbnb) or performance-based contracting (payment for the final performance e.g.: Rolls Royce) have revolutionised entire industries. Therefore, many companies have changed their model to move from pure product sales to the sale of problem solutions and services. When servitization moves a manufacturer all the way to becoming a solution provider there are major changes on the business model.

For enabling this transition, several frameworks are described in the literature [Niemann Jörg, 2016] [Niemann Jörg, Tichkiewitch Serge, 2009].

Figure 2 shows a modified and advanced model based on Bucherer [2010] which is applied for the development of a new business model on the basis of an existing model. It consists of several phases in which different activities are pro-posed. After each phase there is a gate which requires a verification, if the planned solutions and the meaningfulness of the concepts are given. When this is fulfilled the next phase starts, otherwise there is a need to start from scratch with the previous phase. This model is to be understood as a cycle and should serve to question and optimize the business model during the entire life cycle.

Methodology for Transformation

A methodology is defined as “a system of broad principles or rules from which specific methods or procedures may be derived to interpret or solve different problems within the scope of a particular discipline. Unlike an algorithm, a methodology is not a formula but a set of practices.” [Schallmo Daniel R.A., 2017]. To develop and refine the method presented in this paper, the large number of methods found in literature have been evaluated and matched with the practical experience of industrialists. This helps to increase the acceptance and practicability. [Kohne Andreas, 2020] [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021] [55 Pattern Cards, 2013] [Gassmann; Frankenberger; Csik]

On the other hand it is essential to train potential future users in the application of these methods. Therefore it was also an essential part of the methodology to simultaneously develop a training course for academics to train the required skills for later practical application when developing a “XaaS”. The target group of the dedicated training course ranges from students up to top management. This requires a modular course model according to the specific needs of the target groups. [Doleski Oliver D., 2015] [Chizzoli; Raccagni; Busacca, 2020]

Steps and methods

Phase of business Analysis

Enterprises are in general complex bodies with many elements and internal and external interdependencies. Concerning the business model transformation the following main areas must be analyzed: The own business model, the stakeholder and the external influences on the business (ecosystem). [Brugger Ralph, 2009]

Step 1 – Enterprise As- Is Analysis

A review on the existing literature lists the following methods to be the most suitable and applicable in operational business:

- SWOT [Niemann, 2016] [Niemann, Tichkiewitch, 2009] [Kohne, 2020]
- Benchmarking [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021] [Niemann; Pisl, 2021]
- Ishikawa diagram [Niemann, 2016] [Niemann, Tichkiewitch, 2009] [Fussenecker, et al., 2020]

Step 2 – Enterprise goal definition

On the top level each enterprise has defined a vision and according business goals. [Kohne, 2020] The mainly applied methods to master these essential task are according to literature:

- Goal pyramid [Kohne, 2020]
- Gap analysis [Niemann, 2016] [Kohne, 2020]

- Scenario analysis [Niemann, 2016] [Niemann, Tichkiewitch, 2009]

Phase of design

This phase deals with the methodical development of the the new business model. Today’s enterprises perform this step by installing working groups or teams. The advantage of this mode is to generate more ideas and to base all decisions on the group which leads to a better acceptance in the following implementation phase. But -of course in any case- the design of the new business odel has to be in compliance with the enterprise standards, strategy, goals and capabilities.

Step 3 - Business model idea creation

The idea finding is mostly based on creativity of the groups/teams. As previously mentioned this process step is performed under the inclusion several “internal parties/departments” to reach a maximum output of ideas and simultaneously a maximum acceptance of the found solutions.

A crucial aspect is to integrate the voice of the customer as early as possible into the process. All solutions must be re-checked with the (potential) customer needs to ensure the economic success of the later service. Most of the unsuccessful business ideas die because of the weak integration/consideration of customer needs. [Niemann, 2016]

Creative thinking methods help to design completely new business solutions apart from the existing models and current boundaries. [Barsh, Capozzi, Davidson, 2020] In literature but also in practical industrial application the most commonly used methods are “mind mapping” and “brainstorming. For operational enterprise transformation literature references the following tools:

- Destroy your business [Gassmann; Frankenberger; Csik]
- The empathy map [Chizzoli; Raccagni; Busacca, 2020]
- St. Galler business model navigator [Brugger, 2009]

Step 4 - Detailed business model design

After some ideas have been gathered, they should be thought through systematically. All aspects should be considered, to enable a holistic perspective of the business model and to ensure its functionality. For this the most proven tools used in practice are

- Business Canvas [Kreutzer, 2017] [Chizzoli; Raccagni; Busacca, 2020]
- SIPOC [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021] [Niemann, 2017a]

Step 5- Business model evaluation

The final step of the process is the evaluation of the business model. This step is rather difficult because so far there are no data available that could be used for the impact/market success evaluation or analysis of key performance indicators (KPIs). Therefore a lot of assumptions and estimations need to be made. Anyway the literature lists several tools and methods to perform such an analysis in a methodic process including internal as well as external parameters.:

- PESTEL [Barsh; Capozzi; Davidson, 2020]
- Porters five forces [Barsh; Capozzi; Davidson, 2020]
- Value benefit analysis [Niemann, 2017b]

Phase of implementation

After the final approval of the management the transformed business model (or newly developed business model) has to be rolled-out for business operation. This requires a roll-out plan that includes the targeted markets/segments, tools and responsibilities.

Step 6 - Solution design

According to several authors a successful solution design can be reached by the following tools/methods:

- Detailed process design [Niemann, 2016] [Niemann; Tichkiewitch, 2009] [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021]
- Resource & investment plan [Niemann, 2016] [Niemann; Tichkiewitch, 2009] [Niemann, Reich, Stöhr, 2021] [Niemann; Fussenecker; Schlösser, 2019]
- Business case [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021] [Niemann; Fussenecker; Schlösser, 2019] [Glauner, 2016]
- Performance management [Doleski, 2015] [Stöhr, et al. 2018]

Step 7 - Implementation strategy

Central objective of the implementation strategy is to master the transformation with a minimum of delays and downtimes. Furthermore an implementation strategy needs to describe the required resources and tools for the operation of the new services and business model. Some authors recommend to run the old and new process for a period in parallel until the new process has reached a certain stability. For the management the toolbox of project management can be applied. [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021], [Barsh; Capozzi; Davidson, 2020]

Common tools and methods listed in literature as well as in practical industrial application are the following:

- Project charter [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021]
- Action plan [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021]
- RACI matrix [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021]
- Project plan [Niemann; Reich; Stöhr, 2021]
- Transformation plan [Gassmann; Frankenberger; Csik] [Doleski, 2015]

Phase of control

As a last step it is recommended to implement a continuous and structured controlling of the implementation and market progress of the new business model. Continuous monitoring of the operational activities and financial figures allows to benchmark the actual with the planned performance. It is essential monitor the market activities and the business impact of the new business/service to identify deviations from planned business goals as soon as possible. The early identification of deviations enables an early reaction to deviations and according improvements of processes or of the product/service.

Step 8 – Continuous performance monitoring

Derived from literature and industrialists the following tools have been identified to be suitable:

- Balance scorecard [Doleski, 2015] [Brugger, 2009] [Niemann, 2017a] [Niemann, 2017b] [Glauner, 2020]
- Break even analysis [Doleski, 2015] [Brugger, 2009] [Niemann, 2017b] [Niemann; Fussenecker; Schlösser, 2019] [Glauner, 2020]
- Rolling forecast [Doleski, 2015] [Brugger, 2009] [Glauner, 2020] [Niemann; Fussenecker; Schlösser, 2019]

Development of a training program

The challenges outlined above place enormous demands on the developers of services in the future. Therefore, the goal was to develop a consistent methodology for the development of services, which takes up and implements these requirements. In this context, a training course was developed at the Flix Research Centre for Life Cycle Excellence at the University of Applied Sciences Duesseldorf. The target group of the course are engineering students and professionals (see fig. 3). The course teaches the basics of designing and developing modern services using "hands-on" training modules. The ratio

of theory and practical units/time is 30%/70%. All practical parts are group works in virtual classrooms with strong interaction and use of digital tools (e.g. for visualization, design etc.)

Fig. 3. Service Engineering training course [source: own graph]

<p>Day 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction • Business Models • Principles of Service Development • Design Thinking • Problem finding 	<p>Day 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphazise • Expert Interview • Mind Mapping • Define • Persona • Presentation 	<p>Day 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideation • Brainwriting • Value Propostion Canvas • Presentation
<p>Day 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototyping • Test • Improvement • Presentation 	<p>Day 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7Ps marketing for services • Tiered pricing odel • Presentation 	<p>Day 6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation Service • Course evaluation Q&A • Examination • Certificates

Fig. 4. Course content [source: own graph]

Fig. 4 shows a rough overview of the topics, methods and practical parts of the course contents.

The course participants develop and design a service step by step using methods and tools that are learned and tested within the course. In this way, the course participants simultaneously learn the

methodological tools in a creative course atmosphere according to the needs identified from the literature and the industry survey. The course lasts approximately five days. Due to the modular design of single units the course content can be extended or shortened depending on the group of participants and the objectives. E.g. students normally need more theoretical input in comparison to industrial participants who are more focused on the practical exercises.

The course ends with a theoretical (online) test and an oral presentation of the developed service. Participants will get an automated certificate in case of successful participation. By this, the course is not only suitable in a face-to-face but also in a 100% online format. However, experiences before COVID 19 always stated that face-to-face formats are advantageous in situations of group works. The found mode via web allows to include a large number of group works into virtual rooms. After two years of training the authors observed a “getting used to” handle meetings in virtual rooms. Essential is to always trigger communication among the participants and to motivate them using digital tools for their work. The course language and the teaching materials are in English so that the course meets industrial standards and is not open for an international “roll-out” among students and industrialists.

Summary and outlook

The paper describes a process and a toolbox of methods for the digital business transformation. To gather the steps and to form them to a process a literature review has been executed to identify methods used in literature and industry. According to the findings FliX research centre has developed a certified training course in the field of service engineering for students and business professionals. The methods and processes found formed the basis for the elaboration of an academic training course in the field of service engineering. The course has been initially designed to bridge the COVID situation with the legal arrangement of distance learning in German universities. The course contains theoretical and practical knowledge of service engineering and includes more than 70% of practical group works. So far more than 60 students have participated in the course. Initially designed for the pandemic situation the course is now open for “transfer”. The online mode with group works in virtual classrooms can be easily transferred on an international level with partners and participants from all over the world. Besides looking for a suitable funding possibility, recommendations for further adjustments are welcome. A proposal is to set up a new online and onsite class to train the future European service engineers within a network of interested universities.

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